

Franziska Crell

18.05.2006

632_Hayu

Source:

Michailovsky, Boyd (1988). La Langue Hayu
PL 3801.V2 MIC 1988

Michailovsky, Boyd (2003). "Hayu". In: Thurgood & LaPolla. The Sino-Tibetan Languages. Routledge, p. 518-532
PL 3521 SIN 2003

I. Language Profile:

Population: 1,743 (2001 census).

Ethnic population: 1,821 (2001 census) to 2,826 (2000).

Region: Nepal - Janakpur Zone, Ramechhap and Sindhuli districts, on the hills on both sides of the Sun Kosi River.

Alternate names: Hayu, Vayu, Wayo, Wayu

Dialects: Distinct from Chepang.

Classification: [Sino-Tibetan](#), [Tibeto-Burman](#), [Himalayish](#), [Mahakiranti](#), [Kham-Magar-Chepang-Sunwari](#), [Chepang](#)

Language use: Hodgson said it was becoming extinct in the mid-19th century, but it has survived until the end of the 20th century (Michailovsky 1988). No monolingual children (Matisoff 1991).

Comments: Now strong Nepali influences in phonology, lexicon, and grammar (J. Matisoff 1991). Recognized as an official nationality by the Government of Nepal. 1,000 to 1,500 meters. Traditional religion.

II. Morpheme Types

i. root

ii. postposed restricted formative

V: AGR, tense, applicative, assertive

ex. buk 'get up'
buk-ŋo 'I get up'
get.up-1s.NPST

N: plural / collective k^hata, INDEF, VOC, CLASS

(case is marked by postpositions – signal the syntactic function of their host which is a subordinated proposition, gerund)

iii. particles

- marker for verb negation: ex. ma, mak^ht for finite indicative
- particles with rhetoric functions: follow te element to which they are applied, follow postpositions if there is one, e.g. ko 'TOP'
- particles with syntactic functions (case)
- particles applying to finite clauses or phrases, e.g. ki 'interrogative', te 'insistance'

ex. ma dzo:nom paha ma na dzo:nom
 NEG 1s.2sO.eat.ASS CIT NEG EMPH 1s.2sO.eat.ASS
 'I won't eat you, I tell you, I won't eat you.'

III. Syllable

syllable canon: (C₁)V(C₂)

- a simple intervocalic C is syllabified as the onset of the following syllable
- in an intervocalic sequence of two consonants the syllable boundary is between the consonants
- in syllables starting in a V, a glottal stop may be inserted preceding the vowel
- morpheme and syllable boundaries almost always coincide

C₁ can be a single consonant or a cluster

inventory of single C₁: k, k^h, g, ŋ, x
 tɕ, dʒ (lamino-palatal)
 tʂ, tʂ^h, dʒ, s (apico-alveolar)
 t, t^h, d, n
 p, p^h, b, m
 r
 l, l̥
 y, w
 h

- /x/, /l̥/ are not attested as syllable initials in word medial syllables
- initial clusters are relatively rare, except in phonasthetic adverbs:
kl, k^hl, gl, kr, k^hr, gr, pl, p^hl, bl

C₂ inventory: p, t, k, m, n, ŋ, r, l, x, ?

IV. Phonological Word

- consist of one or more syllables
- the inventory of syllable final segments of non-word final syllables is richer than the inventory of syllable final segments of word final syllables: additional [x], [ʔ]

- [ʔ] and [x] are in complementary distribution: [x] appears before syllable initial occlusives of the following syllable; [ʔ] appears before sonorants as initials of the following syllable
 - opposition in vowel length and nasality holds only in an open syllable which is the first syllable of a polysyllabic word
- ex.: /tsĩ:ko/ 'fulfill it!'
 /tsi:ko/ 'split it!'
 /niha/ [niha] ~ [nihã] 'the day after tomorrow'
- within a word a syllable final consonant is never followed by a syllable initial vowel

V. Phonotactics

- closed syllable vowels are realized as short
 - nasality on vowels occurs only on open non-word final syllables
 - almost all nasal vowels are long and precede an initial stop, /s/, /l/ or /r/ of the following syllable
 - a slight glottal stop separates a sequence of two identical vowels within a word
 - /y/ appears before all vowels, /w/ only before /a/ and /o/
- syllable initial C:
 - opposition between the apico-alveolar and lamino-palatal series and the opposition between /x/ and /s/ are neutralized before front vowels, realization being apico-alveolar
 - /x/ has the allophone [x^w] before /a/ and /o/
 - syllable final C:
 - syllable final /x, ʔ/ do not occur if word finally
 - [x] occurs only before voiceless stops
 - [ʔ] occurs only before sonorants
 - each final stop has two allophones, voiced and voiceless: voiced allophone occurs before a voiced initial stop either within the same word or between words in very close juncture (voicing is not interrupted during the pronunciation of the final voiced allophone and the pronunciation of the initial voiced stop) – it is realized with glottalization or laryngealization
 - ex.: /ɪt bi to/ [ɪɖbi to] 'permit him to speak'
 - in all other contexts syllable final stops are realized unreleased and accompanied by a glottal stop
 - final /x/ is realized as [ç] after front vowels and [x] after back vowels and /a/
- inventory of verb root final segments is the same as word finally
 - verb roots ending in vowel realize this vowel as long vowel before a suffix attaches
 - inventory of suffix initial consonants: k, ŋ, tɕ, ts, ts^h, s, t, n, m, y, l
 - suffixes never start with a vowel

VI. Morphophonology

apply at the boundary between verb root and suffix

The affixation within a word is in general limited to verbs. Other lexemes allow the affixation of postpositions and some suffixes. The boundaries of these junctures resemble word boundaries concerning phonotactics.

The author of the grammar considers a syntagma consisting of a non-verb and its postpositions and suffixes as one word due to its intonational properties which indicate one word instead of a group of words. But he does not give any details about intonation and prosody.

i. Neutralization of suffix initials conditioned by root finals

after bilabial root final C, there is no opposition between velar and bilabial initials, the archiphoneme being realized as bilabial (the resulting homorganic combinations are subject to the rules below)

ii. Alternations in root final consonants conditioned by suffix initial consonants

a) root final stops are realized as [x] before homorganic suffix initial consonant

b) root final stops are realized as [ʔ] before homorganic nasal or liquid consonant as suffix initial

c) root final nasal consonants are realized as vowel length and nasality before homorganic suffix initial stops (this also applies to the realization of /n/ before /s/)

d) before the homorganic suffix initial nasal, a root final nasal is deleted, leaving an open root syllable with a distinctively short vowel. In contrast, the root syllable of forms of lexically open roots is always realized as long

ex. /piŋ+ŋo/ [piŋo] 'he sews it for me'

vs. /pi+ŋo/ [pi:ŋo] 'he sends me'

e) before suffix initial /s/ or /tʰ/, root final /t/ is deleted, leaving an open root syllable with a distinctively short vowel

ex. /sɪt+sʊŋ/ [sɪsʊŋ] 'he killed me'

vs. /sɪ+sʊŋ/ [sɪ:sʊŋ] 'he knew me'

These rules apply whenever their conditions are met. Other junctures between morphemes are looser than that between verb and suffix. Before postpositions, i. and ii.c) do not apply; ii.a) applies optionally; ii.b), ii.d) apply generally.

iii. Morpheme-specific alternations

– initial /h/ of the postpositions /-ha/ and /-he/ following a syllable final occlusive of the preceding syllable can be realized as voiceless nasal homorganic to the preceding stop

ex.: /got-ha/ [gotʰŋa] ~ [gotʰha] 'with the hand'

VII. Stress

no information about stress and prosody

